

Science

A CASE STUDY ON THE AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF BAHUPITTA KAMALA WSR JAUNDICE

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Abstract

Modern culture and advanced technology have made life comfortable, but it's given invitation to many diseases. In fast life style of people are leading irregular eating habits, eating outside has become fashion which increased risk of contaminated food and water. All these etiological factors lead to risk of related disorders. Bahupitta kamla is one of important disease. Jaundice is a condition in which yellowness of skin, sclera, mucus membrane, and excretions occurs due to hyperbilirubinemia and depositions of bile pigments.

Jaundice is described as kamala vyadhi in Ayurveda. IN ayurvedic samhita description of kamala is given in detail. The description of hepatocellular jaundice is similar to ayurvedic description of kamala vyadhi. Here a case report of a 30 years male having Bahupitta Kamala (Jaundice) who was treated with ayurvedic medicine and some panchakarma which give effective results with ayurvedic management.

Keywords: Hyperbilirubinemia; Bahupitta Kamla; Hepatocellular Jaundice; Ayurvedic Management.

Cite This Article: Dr. Vaishnavi Narahari Saka, and Dr. Vivek S. Chandurkar (2018). "A CASE STUDY ON THE AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF BAHUPITTA KAMALA WSR JAUNDICE." *International Journal of Research - Granthaalayah*, 6(9), 29-33. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1435210>.

1. Introduction

In fast life style of competitive world human being taken far away from nature. Different new eating habits like Pittakara ahar like spicy food, chinese food, vada pav, missal etc. and alcohol consumption tendency also increasing day by day.

Most of times patient just come with sick and tired, later it gets diagnosed as Kamala(jaundice). The incidence of such diseases increasing day by day. Hepatocellular jaundice is a particular form of jaundice, in which skin, eyes, urine become yellowish, indicating excess bilirubin which is bile pigment in the blood. Patient also complains of fatigue and anorexia and nausea [1].

In all ayurvedic texts nidanapanchak and treatment of kamala given very well. “kamali tu virechana” is chikitsa sutra of kamala [2]. The treatment of kamala(jaundice) must start with virechana(purgation). Major cause is raktadushti for kamala vyadhi and yakrut (liver) is mulsthana of rakta. Rakta and pitta has ashraya-ashrayisambhanda so that a daily virechana(purgation) is recommended. The combination of some herbs is also useful in kamala chikitsa. In few conditions medication is not required, just rest and few supplement will be sufficient. In some conditions medical treatment does not work, in such case surgical help may required.

Its one attempt to management of bahupitta kamala with some ayurvedic herbs and panchakarma, which give effective result.

A Case Report as Follows

A 30 year old male patient came to us with **chief complaints of [3]**

- Udarshool (Aabdominal pain)
- Netragat Araktavarnata (Redness of eyes)
- Twak,Mala,Mutra,Netra pitata(Yellowness of skin,stool,urine,eyes)
- khudha mandya (Anorexia)
- hrullhas (Nausea)

Patient had above complaints since 6 months

History

No h/o - HTN, DM, asthma

History of Personal Illness

The patient was normal before 6 months ago. Since then patient had suffering from udarashula (Abdominal pain), netragata araktavarnata (Redness of eyes), twak maka mutra nrtra pittata(Yellowness of skin, stool, urine eyes), kshudha mandya(Anorexia), hrullas (Nausea). For ayurvedic treatment he came to our hospital Seth Sakharam Nemchand Jain Ayurvedic Rugnalaya in kayachikitsa dept. OPD. We admitted patient in IPD section for better management.

Personal History

Alcoholism since last 10 years.

O/E-

Nadi (Pulse)	- 68/min
Mala (Stool)	- Malavshtambha(Constipation)
Mutra (Urine)	- Peetavarniya
Jivha (Tongue)	- Samata
Kshudh (Appetite)	- Mandya
Shabdha (Speech)	- Prakrut (Normal)
Sparsha(Skin)	- Peetavarniya
Druk (Eyes)	- Arakta pitata
Akruti	-madhyam
Bal	-madhyam
Raktadab (BP)	- 110/70

2. Material and Method

1) Method

Centre of the study – S.S.N.J. ayurvedic hospital solapur.
Simple random single case study

2) Material

Table 1: Showing material of case study

Sr. No.	Dravya	Dose	Duration	Anupan
1	Nimb	2gm	1pack(6gm) + 2cups(100ml) water =Half cup(12ml)	-
2	Patol	2gm	(Kwath nirmiti)	-
3	Daruharidra	2gm		-
4	Haritaki	2gm	Given twice in day	-
5	Kutaki	2gm		-
6	Patha	2gm		-
7	Arogyavardhini vati	500mg	Twice in a day	Warm water
8	Mouktik kamudha	yukta 500mg	Twice in a day	Warm water
9	Chandrakala ras	500mg	Twice in a day	Warm water
10	Trivruttavleha	5mg	HS	Warm water

3. Discussion

Hetu of kamala [4]

1) Ahar

- madyana
- kshara-amla-lawana-usha ahar.
- viruddhara

2) Vihar

- chhardi veg dharan (Suppression of natural urges)
- divaswap (Sleeping at day time)

3) Mansika nidan

- kama,chinta,bhaya and krodha

4. Samprapti

Table 2: Showing the Samprapti ghatak [5]

Dosh	Pitta dosh
Dushya	Ras, Rakta, Mansa dhatu
Adhishtana	Rakta, Mansa
Srotas	Rasavaha,Raktavaha,Annava
Vyaktisthan	Twaka

Table 3: Showing the Samprapti bhanga with dravyas used in chikitsa [6-14]

Nimb [6]	Kandughna, pittahara, ruchya,dipan
Patol [7]	Pittasarak,dipan,rechan,krumighna,yakrut uttejaka
Daruharidra [8]	Kandughna, pittahara, yakrut uttejak, dipan
Haritaki [9]	Pittaghna, pittavirechaka, anuloman,rasayani,jwaraghna,dipan,kamalahara
Kutaki [10]	Rechak, dipan, raktashuddhikara, malabhedani
Patha [11]	Rakatshodhak
Aarogyavardhini vati [12]	Regulation of pitta secretion, maintain healthy fluid level in the body,agnidipan,pachana, grahanidoshnashak
Mouktik yukt kamdudha [13]	Pittahara,dahashamak
Chandrakala ras [14]	Pittahara,dahashamak,raktashodhak
Trivruttavaleha	Anuloman,pittaghna

Table 4: Showing changes in blood investigation after chikitsa

Test	30/08/17	6/09/17
Sr. bilirubin(total)	25.4	7.8
Sr.bilirubin(direct)	13.2	5.2
Sr.bilirubin(indirect)	12.2	2.6

Before treatment 30/08/17

after treatment 06/09/17

5. Conclusion

On the basis of above description it can be concluded that ayurved still test to time and its have details description with chikitsa of kamla(jaundice).Ayurved is much more about concerned towards the health of patient due to which there is description of a lot of medicines of jaundice

according to the nature and nurture of patient. In bahupitta kamla mainly pitta dosha is mainly vitiated. Acharya Charaka has described Mruduvirechan chikitsa for bahupitta kamla. Virechan chikitsa has the quality to eliminate the vitiated dosha. Nishottara is the Sukhavirechak [15].

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